

ZENODO openAIRE e-publishing - Paid for by the European Union powered by CERN (Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire)

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Peer reviewed by Swabian (www.swabian.org),
completed on October 24th, 2023

The Perils of Over-Diagnosis in Rare Diseases: A Call for Prudent Clinical Practice

The allure of diagnosing a rare disease can sometimes overshadow the fundamental principles of medical practice. This short paper aims to highlight the challenges and potential pitfalls of over-diagnosing patients with rare diseases, emphasizing the importance of experiential knowledge, intuition, and patient-centered care. First of all, medical textbooks and guidelines are tailored-made for known diseases. As a result, these resources often fall short when confronted with the enigmatic world of rare diseases. The inherent lack of data and unpredictable trajectory of these conditions necessitates a unique clinical approach. Over-diagnosing a patient with a rare disease can lead to several detrimental outcomes:

- Unnecessary testing: any test performed on a patient with a rare disease may expose the patient to agonizing uncertainties with no therapeutic benefit.

- Delay of valuable time: The time lost for the diagnosis of a secondary disease with no foreseeable clinical consequence may delay an improved treatment of the actual underlying disease.
- Psychological impact: The emotional toll associated with a rare disease diagnosis cannot be underestimated. An endless series of check-ups can lead to psychological complications ranging from undue stress to anxiety for the patient and family to iatrogenic trauma.

While medical guidelines offer invaluable direction for known diseases, their applicability wanes with rare conditions.

The lack of data makes predictions based on known trajectories unfeasible. For instance, while a symptom may follow a predictable course in a well-known ailment, it may manifest differently in a rare condition. The experience and intuition of a physician play a pivotal role in diagnosing rare diseases. Rare diseases often present with totally atypical manifestations, requiring physicians to rely on their clinical judgment rather than textbook knowledge. A seasoned physician's gut feeling, shaped by years of experience, can be instrumental in identifying subtle clinical cues that may be overlooked by less experienced colleagues. Given the unpredictable nature of rare diseases, routine check-ups often prove futile. Without a known trajectory, these appointments might not yield significant insights, leading to wasted resources and missed opportunities for timely intervention.

Real-time diagnostic tools (including point-of-care testing) enable immediate clinical decision making tailored to the patient's current

condition and should be used as first-line tools when available.

Physicians should resist the temptation to fall back on their routine pathways. Instead, every clinical decision should be deliberate, informed by the unique presentation of the patient before them.

Diagnosing rare or as yet nameless diseases is difficult, but organizing follow-up is an even weightier problem for the physicians responsible. Rare diseases require deviation from routine clinical procedures, guidelines, one is thrown back on one's basic biological and anatomical knowledge. Physicians must be aware of the dangers of under-diagnosis, misdiagnosis, and over-diagnosis and be prepared to approach each case with a complete lack of bias. This is usually under conditions of polypharmacy. Through a patient-centered approach and the use of point-of-care diagnostics, as well as the new capabilities of telemedicine, clinicians can ensure that their decisions are both informed and effective.

In our practice, we use the following approach:

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

External funding

None.

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